

**VUNOKLANG MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL
OF SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY EDUCATION**
(Faculty of Education, Modibbo Adama University, Yola)
ISSN: 2276-8114

Available online at <https://vmjste.com.ng>

**EFFECTS OF EDMODO LEARNING NETWORK ON STUDENTS' ACHIEVEMENT AND
RETENTION IN ELECTRONICS III IN POLYTECHNICS IN SOUTH-EAST, NIGERIA**

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15016068>

ABSTRACT

This study examined the effects of the Edmodo Learning Network on Students' Achievement and Retention in Electronics III in Polytechnics of South-East, Nigeria. This study was guided by two objectives and corresponding research questions, and hypotheses, a quasi-experimental non-randomized design was employed, sampling 60 students; 30 in experimental group and 30 in control group. The Electronics III Achievement Test (EAT), developed and validated by the researcher, demonstrated a reliability coefficient of 0.89. The experimental group utilized the Edmodo Learning Network, while the control group received traditional instruction. Research questions were addressed using means and standard deviations, while hypotheses were tested through independent t-tests at a 0.05 significance level. The findings indicated a significant positive effect on both academic achievement and retention for the experimental group. Consequently, the study suggests that the Edmodo Learning Network effectively enhanced motivation and academic performance in the Electronics III course. The researcher recommends integrating Edmodo into the Polytechnic curriculum in North-Central Nigeria to further improve student achievement and motivation in their learning experiences.

Keywords: Edmodo, Learning, Network, Achievement, Retention, Electronics III, Polytechnics

INTRODUCTION

Developing nations like Nigeria and many others have come to recognize the importance of innovations in technologies as a catalyst for national development. The Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN, 2013) asserted that the increasing globalization driven technology has made it imperative for Nigeria as an emerging market to irreversibly consider the utilization and promotion of technologies as best practices in education to facilitate her rapid growth and development. According to FlexiSAF (2023) education is widely recognized as a key driver of progress in developed and developing countries such as; Nigeria is no exception. Being heavily populated, the future of Nigeria's success depends to a great extent on its education system and is the bedrock of development of any country (FlexiSAF, 2023). As important as education is recognized in Nigeria, its educational system faces a lot of challenges such as inadequate infrastructure, insufficient teaching materials and methods, and a shortage of qualified teachers among others (Idoko, 2024). The low/poor performance and failure rate of students in examinations has raised concerns over system issues like unqualified teachers dotting the educational landscape (Afolabi, 2014). The low performance or failure rate is not different with electronics courses offered at the polytechnics education system of South-East, Nigeria.

According to Ogundola, Abiodun, and Jonathan in Atsumbe, Owodunni, Raymond and Uduafemhe (2018) this failure to meet expected standards is attributable to the continuous use of unsuitable instructional methodologies (mostly a traditional didactic instructional delivery approach) by teachers. According to Afolabi (2024) the Vice Chancellor, Hallmark University, Ijebu-Itele, Ogun State, Professor Segun Odunola called on the government to carry out an in-depth investigation to know the reasons for the failure rates to avert the trend. He also called on the government to provide adequate funding for education to provide necessary infrastructures in the classrooms and make a conducive environment for teaching and learning. He also called for an update of teachers' knowledge by exposing them to modern teaching methodologies and on-the-job retraining. To this end, due to the persistent failure rates in examinations, Idoko (2024) suggests integrating innovative technologies in education that could offer a lasting solution. These are the sources of worry that inform the researcher to investigate the Effect of Edmodo Learning Network on students' achievement and retention in Electronics III in polytechnics of North-Central, Nigeria where the failure rate prevails.

Educational technology (commonly abbreviated as edutech, or edtech) according to Wikipedia (2024) is the process of integrating technology into education in a positive manner that promotes a more diverse learning environment and a way for students to learn how to use innovative technologies as well as their common assignments. It is the combined use of computer hardware, software, and educational theory and practice to facilitate learning. Loyola (2024) defines educational technology as the field of study that investigates the process of analyzing, designing, developing, implementing, and evaluating the instructional environment, learning materials and so on, in order to improve teaching and learning process. Loyola (2024) further narrated that educational technology in education is very vital since it helps today's teachers to integrate innovative technologies and tools into their classroom. Therefore teachers/lecturers could upgrade and improve on the learner-centeredness of their classrooms. Also, they could engage their students in a unique, innovative, and equitable ways. Edmodo learning network is one of such educational technology platforms for teachers/lecturers, students as well as parents (Wikipedia, 2024).

The Edmodo Learning Network, as described by According to Trust (2012) Edmodo Learning Network is described as an interactive platform resembling social networking sites, enabling collaborative learning among teachers and students. Developed by O'Hara and Nic Borg in 2008, Edmodo serves as a learning management system (LMS) designed to enhance communication, collaboration, and knowledge sharing among lecturers, students, and parents in a secure educational environment. Brinton and Chiang (2014) highlight Edmodo as an innovative technology that functions as a blended learning interface applicable to various educational courses. Edmodo learning network is referred to as an educational technology platform meant for teachers, students and their parents has encompassed e-learning, instructional technology, information and communication technology (ICT) in education, edtech, learning technology, multimedia learning, technology-enhanced learning (TEL), computer-based instruction (CBI), computer managed instruction, computer-based training (CBT). Yunkuel and Cankaya (2017) pointed out that, Edmodo learning platform has been found useful in a classroom through a variety of applications that allows students to connect with each other and their teachers as well as evaluate student's achievement or performance. Edmodo learning network enabled teachers to share content, distribute quizzes and assignments, and manage communication with students, colleagues, and parents.

Achievement is defined as the successful completion of a task or objective. Specifically, academic achievement pertains to the success students achieve in their educational endeavors, often assessed through their academic performance, progress, and attainment of learning goals. Hattie and Donoghue (2016) describe academic achievement as the mastery of

subject matter knowledge and skills, while Anni and Kalle (2016) characterize it as the extent to which a learner benefits from specific instruction. Retention can be referred to the extent to which a learner has attained their short or long-term educational goals. According to TopHat (n.d.), it is the measurement of the amount of academic content a student learns in a given time frame. Retention is usually assessed through frequent progress and comprehension checks and examinations; such as formative and summative assessments that are usually conducted at intervals (i.e., quizzes, mid-term test and final test) were used to measure students' knowledge retention. However, there is no consensus on how it is best evaluated or which elements of it are most important. Notwithstanding, Technology provides students with easy-to-access information, accelerated learning, and fun opportunities to practice what they learn and achieve better results (Soeonline, 2020).

Also, student retention can be effectively described as taken in information and the ability to recall it in the future. It is the process of transferring new information into long-term memory (Lorman, 2024). It is all making new information stick and finding effective ways to do this. Technology makes learning more interactive and engaging like Edmodo learning network. For instance, students can use apps, simulations, and games to learn a concept. This learning method millennially is more effective as it appeals to different learning styles, making it easier for students to retain information (Educatly, 2024). Therefore, retention refers to the ability of a student to recall, memorize and replicate learnt concepts. It could also be referred to as the ability to remember experiences and things learnt, especially when presented. Polytechnic education is known as technical college or Institutes of technology which offer programs that are designed to prepare students for immediate entry into workforce. At the polytechnic education, Electronics III course is an important course for ND II and is mainly on general nature of positive and negative feedback in systems (Ojo-Williams, 2021).

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

There has been low achievement of students studying electronics III course in the polytechnics over the years. According to Jack (2017) this has caused them to be found lacking in knowledge and skills in the world of works. Their inability to demonstrate high understanding of skill is in alignment of the fact that the processes of teaching these days do not boost their academic performance and interest and to learning, since they are the millennial age learners. To this accordance whereof, Kurniawati, Purwasih, Anzari, and Apriadi, (2021) reported that the low academic achievement of students in semester examination in polytechnics which have repeatedly shown failure in electronics III course is due to regular use of conventional methods such as lecture method, discussion and demonstration methods among others which students are fade up with. If the problem of lack of interest, resulting to low retention of students studying electronics III in Polytechnics is not curtailed, the effect will not be limited to: failure to graduate at the appropriate time, lack of employment, low self-esteem, and non-contribution to national development. To this end, it suffices to employ the use of Edmodo learning network in the teaching and learning Electronics III. It is hopeful that Edmodo learning network would boost students' learning and hence drive sustainable retention.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The aim and objectives of this study is to determine the Effects of Edmodo Learning Network on students' Achievement and Retention in Electronic III in Polytechnics of North Central, Nigeria. Specifically, the study seeks to determine:

1. The difference between mean Achievements of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN.

2. The difference between mean Retention scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN?

RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The following research questions were formulated to guide this Study.

1. What is the difference between mean Achievements scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN?
2. What is the difference between mean delayed Retention scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN?

HYPOTHESES

The following null hypotheses are guided this study.

- H₀₁:** There is no significant difference between mean Achievements scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN.
- H₀₂:** There is no significant difference between mean delayed retention scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Concept of Social Learning Network (SLN)

The concepts of social networking refer to the use of Internet-based social media sites to stay connected with friends, family, colleagues, customers, and others. Edtech (2020) pointed out that although Social Learning Networks have been around for quite some time before now, but it is a more recent phenomenon in the use of education. ET Spotlight (2020) has it that social networking through social sites such as Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, LinkedIn used as social networks. Others include: Instagram, YouTube, Reddit, Quora, Digg, among many more, used for different purposes. According to Opkomu, Ebika & Mercy (2018), social networks applications are becoming explosive within the educational system today. Some examples of such educational social networks include through social sites such as: Facebook, WhatsApp, Twitter, LinkedIn, Edmodo, amongst many others, which are used as social networks. Opkomu, Ebika & Mercy (2018) continued that these educational networks are where many students become involved to collaborate with their teachers on academic matters such as research or projects for school, or to interact with professors and teachers via blogs and classroom forums.

Concept of Edmodo Learning Network

Edmodo learning platform was created by Nic Borg and Jeff O'Hara, who were school district Information Technology Professionals (ITP), the two founders created Edmodo learning platform in 2008 to adapt a fast and sharing tool to the security and privacy needs of a school environment. Al-Kathiri (2014) pointed out that Edmodo learning network has been found to be widely used with numerous certified users as at in the mid-2013. Furthermore, Al-Kathiri (2014) pointed out that, another name used widely for Edmodo learning platform by the founder of Edmodo is "Facebook for schools." Edmodo network was created basically for teaching and learning, whose intention is much more private and safer to use in the educational sector. Therefore, these founders referred to the Edmodo learning platform as "an educational website that takes the ideas of a social network and makes it appropriate on its accuracy and makes it more suitable for classroom

utilization''. Balasubramanian and Fukey (2014) stated that the design of Edmodo platform as a social networking site is specifically to enhance teaching and learning.

In the vain, Social Learning Networks has brought both the educators and learners on the same platform, since learning is mostly done in an interactive environment using one-to-one as well as group discussions. It also provides more choice and greater control to the learners over their academic activities and sources of the materials used in teaching and learning, thereby elevating the natural processes of learning, the above authors are convinced that SLN is more effective than the conventional classroom learning method. Kurt (2019) further explained that Social Learning Networks has brought Changes in the educational landscape for both teachers and students.

Vibhu (2014) stated that Edmodo learning network as an example of the innovative e-learning network and or ICT supported education system. Edmodo learning network is viewed to have involved tools related to web-based learning. Furthermore, Vibhu (2014) refers to Edmodo as an innovative educational instructional delivery used globally which takes the ideas of facebook to improve on it and make it suitable in the classroom utilization across the globe. In the same vein, Dobler (2012) stated that Edmodo learning platform is seen to be social network application meant for lecturers, students, parents, and schools and the community. In the context of using Edmodo learning platform, which students can reach out to one another and connect by sharing ideas, problems, and helpful tips such as: sharing of assignments and grades, host discussions and post videos, schedule lectures and appointments, among others that aims to facilitate teaching and learning in the school environment.

METHODOLOGY

The quasi-experimental research design that employed a pre-test post-test non-equivalent, non-randomized design was used for this study. This design was considered suitable for this study since it made use of the existing intact classes. This study was conducted in North-Central geographical region in Nigeria, specifically; the researcher sampled two polytechnics that offered Electronics III course, they are; Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana, Ebonyi State and Enugu State Polytechnic, Iwollo that have similar facilities and accreditation standard of National Board for Technical Education (NBTE). The researcher sampled 60 students in two Polytechnics that offered Electronics III course. The researcher randomly selected one Polytechnic for experimental group with 30 students and the other with 30 students for the control group. The researcher adapted Electronics III Achievement Test (EAT) for this study using the topics in the modules and course specification of Electronics III course prepared by National Board for Technical Education offering accredited programs (NBTE, 2015) for easy modification to test (NDII) students offering Electrical/Electronic. The researcher prepared two sets of lesson plans for experimental and control groups. Experimental group was taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network contained in the experimental group lesson plan which required treatment, while the control group used the regular conventional lecture method of teaching that required no treatment. The (EAT) instrument was validated by three experts, one expert from Abubakar Tafawa Balewa University, Bauchi. Another expert from Benue State University, Makurdi and an expert from Benue State Polytechnic, Ugbokolo. Each expert was served with a copy of the EAT instrument and was requested to ascertain the validity, suitability and appropriateness of the contents in the items. The researcher ensured that all the inputs, suggestion and modifications made by the experts were corrected before the final copy was produced and used for the study. The instruments were trial tested in the students in the selected polytechnics for this study. The result obtained EAT was analysed using Pearson Product Moment Correlation (PPMC). Its established reliability coefficient yielded 0.87. Madiha and Walid

(2016) suggested that if a coefficient is 0.7 and above, the instrument should be considered significant and reliable for the study. The researcher with the help of one trained research assistants administered EAT instrument to the students, prior and after to the students in their examination halls to obtain data for the study.

Data collected for the study were subjected to statistical analysis using. Mean and Standard Deviation was used to answer the research questions while t-test and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to test hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision to uphold or reject any null hypothesis was based on the p-value whether is greater or less than significance level (0.05).

RESULTS

The results of this study are presented according to research questions and their corresponding hypotheses.

Research question 1: What is the difference between mean achievements scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN?

Table 1: Mean Achievement scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo learning network and those taught without ELN

<i>Groups</i>	<i>Group of respondents</i>	<i>N</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Std. Deviation</i>
Experimental and control groups pre-test scores	Experimental group	30	7.8333	2.00144
	Control group	30	7.3333	4.42823
	Pre-test mean difference		.5000	
Experimental and control groups post-test scores	Experimental group	30	39.1333	5.50694
	Control group	30	16.3667	5.44238
	Post-test mean difference		22.7666	

Table1 shows that at pre-test, experimental group had mean achievement of 7.83 with standard deviation of 2.00 while the control group had mean achievement of 7.33 with standard deviation of 4.43. The difference in mean achievement at pre-test is as small as .500. This indicates that the groups have similar knowledge level of Electronics III prior to commencement of the study. At the end of the study, the post-test mean achievement of experimental group was 39.13 with standard deviation of 5.51 while the control group had mean achievement of 16.37 with standard deviation of 5.44. The data indicate that the experimental group significantly outperformed the control group in the post-test, with a mean difference of 22.77. This suggests that the use of the Edmodo learning network had a positive effect on students' achievement in Electronics III. The standard deviations show that there was more variation in the control group's pre-test scores, indicating that the experimental group may have had a more consistent performance. In conclusion, the results suggest that integrating ELN into the learning process can enhance students' achievement in technical subjects, as evidenced by the substantial difference in post-test scores between the groups.

Research question 2: What is the difference between mean retention scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN?

Table 2: Mean Retention scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those without ELN

Group of respondents		N	Mean	Std. Deviation
Experimental Group	Retention Scores	30	33.67	5.83
Control Group	Retention Scores	30	8.00	2.17

The result in Table 2 indicates that the mean retention test score of the experimental group is 33.67 while the control group taught without Edmodo Learning Network had mean retention test score of 8.00. The difference in experimental and control groups was 25.67 indicating that retention test scores of experimental group was 25.67 higher than the control group.

Test of Hypotheses

H0₁: There is no significant difference between mean achievements scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN.

Table 3: Test of significant difference between achievements mean scores of students taught Electronics III using ELN and those taught without ELN

Dependent Variable: (Edmodo) post achievement scores

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	7789.128 ^a	2	3894.564	128.755	.000
Intercept	7059.126	1	7059.126	233.377	.000
PreAch	14.312	1	14.312	.473	.494
Group	7683.455	1	7683.455	254.017	.000
Error	1724.122	57	30.248		
Total	55717.000	60			
Corrected Total	9513.250	59			

a. R Squared = .819 (Adjusted R Squared = .812)

In an analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) examining the effect of teaching method (Electronics III using Electronic Learning Network (ELN) versus conventional methods) on post-achievement scores presented on table 3, the overall model was statistically significant, $F(2, 57) = 128.76, p < .001$, with an R^2 of .819, indicating that approximately 81.9% of the variance in post-achievement scores can be explained by the model. The intercept was also significant, $F(1, 57) = 233.38, p < .001$, suggesting that the mean post-achievement scores differ significantly from zero when controlling for pre-achievement scores. However, the pre-achievement scores did not significantly predict post-achievement scores, $F(1, 57) = .47, p = .494$, indicating that prior knowledge did not account for a significant portion of the variance in post-achievement scores. In contrast, the group variable showed a significant effect, $F(1, 57) = 254.02, p < .001$. This suggests that there was a statistically significant difference in the post-achievement scores between students taught using ELN and those taught without ELN, with a large effect size. These results suggest that the use of ELN in teaching Electronics III significantly enhances student achievement compared to conventional teaching methods.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between mean retention scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN.

Table 4: Test of difference between mean retention scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN

Dependent Variable: Edmodo retention scores

Source	Type III Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	10347.949 ^a	2	5173.974	450.678	.000
Intercept	90.840	1	90.840	7.913	.007
PostArch	466.282	1	466.282	40.615	.000
Group	527.762	1	527.762	45.971	.000
Error	654.385	57	11.480		
Total	37044.000	60			
Corrected Total	11002.333	59			

a. R Squared = .941 (Adjusted R Squared = .938)

In Table 4, reading across row heading ‘group’, shows that $df = 1$, $F = 45.971$ and $Sig. = .000 = p$. Since $p < 0.05$, the observed difference in mean retention scores between the two groups is statistically significant so the hypothesis which stated that there is no significant difference between mean retention scores of students taught Electronics III using Edmodo Learning Network and those taught without ELN is rejected.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The finding of study with respect to students’ Achievement scores revealed that before the treatments or prior to commencement of the study, the students’ knowledge levels on Achievements were measured (Pre-test) and found that they had similar knowledge levels for both groups with the little difference not so significant. The use Edmodo Learning Network instruction to teach Electronics III course as a treatment was discovered to enhance significantly higher Achievement in the experimental group when compared with the conventional method. This finding is in agreement with Ma’azi and Janfeshan (2018) whose study revealed that experimental group performed better than the control group. This is so because with the Edmodo learning network, students in the 21 centuries are millennia aged, therefore they prefer they use of internet facilities for learning. Also, this finding agrees with that of Rias and Hashim (2004) whose findings revealed that, with the advancement of Internet and web-based application Edmodo as an example of social learning platform converts the knowledge/practices of conventional teaching method and assists in the quest knowledge seeking was employed to conduct assessments after classroom hours by broadening the number of resources available to the students, This finding also agrees with Oguguo, Ajuonuma, Azubuike, Ene, Atta and Oko (2020) whose findings of their study revealed that students frequently who engage in social media in order to make new friends, research about their assignments and source for other educational materials, stay up to dates with latest trends and news, were found to have better achievements scores than their control group counterpart.

Another finding on retention revealed that, students taught with ELN had significantly higher retention scores than students taught without Edmodo or conventional method. They are found to perform significantly higher than their counterpart without ELN. This finding also agrees with Oguguo, Ajuonuma, Azubuike, Ene, Atta and Oko (2020) whose findings of their study revealed that students frequently who engage in social media in order to make new friends, research about their assignments and source for other educational materials, stay up to dates with latest trends and news, were found to have better achievements scores than their control group counterpart.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the use of Edmodo learning network had significantly improved achievement of students with prior knowledge in Electronics III course. Also, Edmodo learning network is found to have increased retention rates of students in Electronics III course. The finding also revealed that interfacing Edmodo learning network to teach Electronics III facilitated collaborative learning and engagement among students and their lecturer. It found out that Edmodo's interactive features promoted deeper understanding of complex Electronics concepts.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this Study it was recommended that:

1. The Edmodo learning network should be integrated into the Polytechnic curriculum in South-East, Nigeria to further improve student achievement and motivation in their learning experiences.
2. The policy makers should develop policies that support the implementation and utilization of Edmodo learning network in Nigerian education.
3. Training should be provided for instructors/lecturers to effectively facilitate Edmodo learning network in polytechnics of South-East, Nigeria. Lecturers should use Edmodo learning network to supplement or interface traditional teaching methods in South-East, Nigeria.

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